
Discourse on Media Portrayal of Migration in Africa

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Abstract

This paper adopted the descriptive method to highlight certain global and local media portrayals of migration in Africa. The researcher adopted library research method. It was found that media portrayal of African migrants in South Africa as criminals and job-stealers has fueled xenophobia. Similarly, in countries like Libya and Morocco, local attitudes toward sub-Saharan migrants have worsened due to media-fueled stereotypes. More so, migrants are reduced to passive figures in the media, reinforcing the idea that they are problems to be managed rather than people with agency and goals. It was concluded that the stereotypical depictions of immigrant populations in the media represent a risk-fraught area in which prejudices may inadvertently be furthered. Amongst others, the paper recommended that the media need to avoid unfair prejudicial depictions and start presenting immigrant populations as well-rounded cultural groups, the media may be capable of providing a positive arena for diversity, cultural exchange and acculturation.

Keywords: Media, Portray, Migration and African Culture

Introduction

Popularly known as ‘Japa,’ the migration of Nigerians and other Africans to African and European countries could have earned the continent the poor and disadvantaged image it has today. Migration from Africa commonly evokes the picture of a continent fleeing from its evils towards the European countries. Such alarmist representations of an African mass exodus, fueled by the media and policy makers alike, are actually quite far from the real dynamics of African migration (Kariithi, 2017). In Europe, notably in the traditional destination countries, since the 1970s migration has turned into a politicised topic, increasingly leading to more restrictive migration policies, but it is only in the past few years that it has sparked off a crisis throughout the whole African continent.

Moreover, a lot of persons may have heard, seen or read the subject of migration in the media. This ranges from motion films to still images in the newspapers to tweets on social media, and such coverage may have portrayed migration in one way or another bad, especially to host communities, or simply raised it as a topical issue. To a large extent, people’s perceptions, attitudes or beliefs about migration are based on both direct experiences and those channeled through the lens of the media, although the precise mixture likely depends on one’s individual situations (World Migration report, 2018).

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Media coverage contributes to the perception of immigrants as people capable of constituting nuisance in their host countries (Haynes, Merolla & Ramakrishnan, 2016). This is so because the media is a powerful tool that often affects people's thinking and judgement.

According to *Magri cited in Kariithi (2017)* the EU, ECOWAS, AU and their member states have failed to look below the surface of migration flows as they have repeatedly preferred to turn blind eyes to their root causes.. Contrary to popular perceptions, Kariithi (2017) suggests that, far from being exceptional, the size and destinations of African migration are impressively similar to global migratory patterns. In other words, African migrants too, when crossing an international border, are more likely to move to neighboring countries within their African sub-region than elsewhere, because of the higher costs of moving over longer distances; costs which may ultimately include the loss of their own lives. Actually, if something exceptional has to be found in African migration, it is the striking number of sub-Saharan countries each hosting over two million displaced people in 2016: South Sudan, Sudan, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Somalia, and Nigeria (UNHCR, 2017).

To Abramitzky & Boustan (2017), migration is a complex and multi-faceted phenomenon. Resorting to easy explanations may appear as a convenient shortcut but ultimately, twists the truth. This complexity is only very rarely reflected in the policy choices adopted by receiving countries. By continuously placing the spotlight on border protection and on how European societies are affected by migration flows, they ultimately produce unintended effects. For instance, restrictive European migration policies have caused migrants to diversify their destination countries and to resort to riskier routes and irregular practices. These policies also have a negative impact on migrants' decision to return to their home countries: even if they want to, migrants are less likely to leave Europe if they know it will be difficult to eventually come back (Abramitzky & Boustan, 2017).

As the dust settles after the recent European Parliament election, the results show historical gains for the far-right populist parties in Britain, France, Greece, Austria and Germany. Analysts linked these transformations partially to the growing anti-immigration sentiment in Europe, as people, particularly in bad economic times, tend to resort to scapegoating and blaming migrants for 'stealing' their jobs and housing. It often turns out this way because people are poorly informed about migrants and easily manipulated by the alarmist narratives of far-right politicians. Therefore, instead of acknowledging the increasing diversity of their home countries and recognising how it could enrich societies, people see migrants as 'others' and as threats to the existing social order (Adepoju, 2008).

To Danilova (2014), public attitudes are not wholly shaped by media. However, in the age of globalisation, media become very powerful tools and some of the main determinants of public opinion. Depending on the type of media and the aims behind them, they can either reinforce the criminalised image of a newcomer and underline anti-immigrant rhetoric or on the contrary, help to better integrate migrants and serve as a genuine transmitter of their stories, thus counteracting misunderstanding and fear. To

ensure that the human rights of migrants are protected and that intercultural understanding (where diversity is seen as a positive phenomenon) is built, the local and international communities need to address the power of media and the effects they produce in the public conversation on migration (Danilova, 2014).

The language used in the mainstream media when covering stories about migrants vividly mirrors the existing narrative of migrant as ‘the other’ and shapes it at the same time. Perhaps the clearest articulation of anti-immigration sentiment can be found in the British press. Examining 43 million words (i.e., the content addressing migration in 20 popular British newspapers) between 2010 and 2012, a 2013 report by the Migration Observatory at the University of Oxford, found that the most common word used in relation to “migrants” was “illegal” (Danilova, 2014). Headlines like “Eight-fold increase in the number of illegal migrants entering Europe” are typical. “Failed” turned out to be the most common descriptor of “asylum seekers”, while in order to describe the security concerns and aspects of legality of migration, words such as “terrorist,” “sham” were most commonly used. This kind of language criminalises migrants who often cross borders in vulnerable circumstances.

To Baker, Gabrielatos & McEnery (2013), these words often surge without being substantiated by data, while the media turn out to be far from objective when it comes to migration and rather take a stance through the language they choose. The trend is very alarming as the mainstream media is still often a primary source of information for citizens and its message gets transmitted to the consciousness of listeners and viewers, having an effect on how they relate to the multicultural societies in which they live. Against this backdrop, this paper investigated how local media portrays immigrants and the impression they create in the minds of the public.

Conceptualisation of Migration

Human migration is the movement of people from one place to another with the intention of settling in the new location. When large numbers of people relocate, historians ask questions about why these people moved and what impacts their movements had. Broadly speaking, there are two categories of factors that influence people’s decisions to migrate. Push factors occur where someone is currently living and make continuing to live there less attractive. A push factor could be political unrest, a lack of job opportunities, or overcrowding. Pull factors occur in a potential destination and make it an attractive place to migrate to. A pull factor could be better job opportunities or having relatives or friends who have already moved to this location (Ramaprasad, Lang & Sessa, 2015).

According to Blinder & Allen (2015), migration is widely recognised as a complex phenomenon that cannot be easily reduced to any single factor, but rather results from multiple, overlapping and shifting motives. The common understanding that international migrants essentially respond to global inequalities and geographical differences in wealth, freedom and wellbeing is a helpful but limited starting point, as it cannot explain, for example, why do so *few* people migrate— 244 million in 2015, or just about 3.3% of the world population – nor the reasons why this percentage stayed

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relatively unchanged for at least the past half-century (the figure was 2.4% in 1960 and 2.1% in 1980). Besides economic and political conditions in origin and destination countries, and existing national and international policies, any sound inquiry into this subject must account for the crucial role that a migrant's personal circumstances, and the family and social networks he or she relates to, play in a decision to move that cannot be reduced to a semi-automatic response to external conditions (Blinder & Allen, 2015)

To Okólski (2012), one classic if simplistic way of framing the various explanatory factors that are presumed to lead to migration is to distinguish between a macro, and a micro level. Macro-level causes are structural drivers that, in principle, indistinctly affect each and every potential migrant. A country's demographics, its geographic location and climatic events, economic wealth and performance, established political arrangements and security issues, and migration policies – both with regard to origin as well as to transit and destination countries – all fall into this category. On the opposite side, micro-level conditions include both the long list of an individual's personal features (age, gender, health, language and ethnicity) as well as the resources available to him or her (notably, finances and skills, including education).

In between the two, a less obvious macro-level category accounts for those elements connecting the individual with the broader society, such as an extended family group, ethnic, religious or regional communities, and wider social networks, comprising those powered by internet and the new social media. It is well-documented, for example, that *migrant networks* connecting “migrants, former migrants, and non-migrants in origin and destination areas through bonds of kinship, friendship, and shared community origin decrease the economic, social and psychological costs of migration”, thus favoring the probability that a specific person will embark on the journey as well as affecting how the latter unfolds (Okólski, 2012).

Literature Review

Ever since sub-Saharan countries gained independence back in the 1960s, the region has consistently remained the poorest in the world bar Southern Asia. With a US\$3,922 per capita income at purchasing-power parity in 2016, the area has long been synonymous with development failure: a stagnating region with few signs of change and little prospects of advancement. The peak of disappointment was the “lost decade” of the 1980s and early 1990s, when “devastatingly bad economic performance” led to a visible decline in living standards. By the end of the century, per capita income was at the same level it was in the early 1960s (Ahmad, 2013).

Since around the mid-1990s and then the early 2000s, however, sub-Saharan Africa began to witness quite substantial progress. More optimistic – and at times over-optimistic – assessments made their appearance and rapidly multiplied as if by contagion. By then, many observers deemed Africa “on the move,” “fast-changing,” “in transformation,” or “rising.” While the occasionally hyperbolic accounts risked hiding the extent to which many things remained just as they were – including the lifestyles, resources and vulnerabilities of many remote rural areas, as the current hunger crisis in East Africa reminds us all too clearly – sub-Saharan societies did see the emergence of

new dynamics and important progress. Besides the latter, long-term ongoing processes also continued to unfold, implying additional, if more gradual, changes. Some of the key transformations underway in recent years include massive demographic expansion, remarkable economic performances, technological innovations, social improvements, political renewals, and environmental change. What have been the main implications – if any – for African mobility? —a longing question, yet no answer (Kariithi, 2017)

Apart from civil wars, many countries in Sub-Saharan Africa are plagued with recurring droughts, famine, political conflicts and transitions, as well as unfavorable government policies and poor governance, corruption and even biased media reports that often trigger population movements. These contexts, which are typical of several African countries, remain relevant for a more balanced and comprehensive understanding of Africa's migration systems, together with the relationships between internal and international migration and human wellbeing in the region (Mberu & Pongou, 2012).

In relation to refugees, internally displaced persons (IDPs), asylum-seekers and trafficked persons moving within and out of the region, the UNHCR reported that out of the 65.6 million forcibly displaced people worldwide, 22.5 million were refugees in 2016²⁷. About 10.3 million people were newly displaced by conflict or persecution, which comprises 6.9 million individuals displaced within the borders of their own countries and 3.4 million who were new refugees and new asylum-seekers (Ahmad, 2013).

At the global level, some countries were especially affected by forced displacements in 2016. Syrians continued to be the largest forcibly displaced population, with 12 million people at the end of 2016; that includes 5.5 million refugees, 6.3 million IDPs, and nearly 185,000 asylum-seekers. Colombians were the second-largest group, with 7.7 million forcibly displaced, mostly inside their country. A total of 4.7 million Afghans were also forcibly displaced, of whom 1.8 million were IDPs and 2.9 million were refugees or asylum-seekers. Countries in Africa that in 2016 had over 2 million people displaced, either internally or as refugees or asylum-seekers, include South Sudan (3.3 million), Sudan (2.9 million), the Democratic Republic of Congo (2.9 million), Somalia (2.6 million), and Nigeria (2.5 million). The refugee population from Burundi increased by 39% during 2016, while the IDP population in that country quadrupled to 141,200 people. Conflict and violence also continued in the Central African Republic, the Democratic Republic of Congo, and Sudan leading to new displacements and inhibiting returns. In 2016, the South Sudanese refugee crisis was the fastest-growing in the world, with the latest evidence from UNHCR showing that out of a 2.27 million population of concern in South Sudan, 1.95 million registered as refugees (UNHCR, 2017).

Human trafficking has been acknowledged as the emerging dark side of migration in Africa. Deepening poverty, persistent unemployment, conflicts, human deprivation and expectations of a dismal future have fostered an environment in which human trafficking can flourish. Adepoju identified trafficking in children, mainly for farm labor and domestic work mostly within and across African countries and trafficking in women and young persons for sexual exploitation, mainly outside the region and particularly in the EU, Lebanon and the Gulf States, as two of the three main types of trafficking in the

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region. Child trafficking in sub-Saharan Africa is a demand-driven phenomenon – the existence of an international market for child labor and the sex trade, coupled with an abundant supply of children from poor families. Children are recruited through networks of agents and parents are forced by poverty and ignorance to enlist their children to work as domestic servants in the informal sector or on plantations, hoping to benefit from their wages (McConville, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on framing theory, proposed by Erving Goffman in 1974. Framing theory posit how media shapes public perception by emphasising certain aspects of migration, while agenda-setting theory examines which migration issues receive the most attention. How exactly one or more of the factors actually lead to migration requires a specific *causal* story, that is, a theoretical explanation. And there is no lack of such accounts. In a rather deterministic way, “push-pull” or “gravity” approaches look at international migration as a response to the wide differences in the demographic structure and economic opportunities of individual countries, towards a functional equilibrium. Asymmetric relations between economically advanced and poor countries are also at the basis of a second set of explanations – at times referred to as historical-structural – but in this case the emphasis lies on the uneven and exploitative nature of (mostly labor) migration under global capitalism.

Malit & Youha (2013) opine that human migration, however, is hardly the kind of rational, passive and smooth response to external conditions that both push-pull and historical-structural accounts would posit. Ultimately, an individual chooses to migrate, and this may have to do more – or at least also – with his or her perceptions, aspirations and resources, with risk-sharing and diversification strategies within the family, or with the established mobility patterns of the cultural or regional community he or she belongs to. Recent versions of migration transition theories try to incorporate the role of an individual’s decisions within a macro-level approach. The central tenet is that migration is essentially an intrinsic part of broader processes of social change, usually embodied in the concept of ‘development’, and unfolds in a non-linear way. As societies develop and transform, increased awareness, aspirations and assets make individuals more likely to decide to migrate. But the process also leads to a point where, once a country achieves a certain level of development, the balance between emigration and immigration shifts, with the former declining while the latter increases (Malit & Youha, 2013).

In their efforts to explain mobility, migration studies made several common or common-sense assumptions much more problematic than they at first appear. Far from being a modern phenomenon, migration is found across ages and societies (with a peak of intensity during the XIX century). As a matter of fact, asking why, today, so many people move may not even be the right question: in a global world that is otherwise characterized by freedom of movement – can we imagine a situation in which only 3% of supermarket products, television programs, websites or books come from abroad? – the share of migrants over the world population actually looks abnormally low.

Also, there is now widespread consensus that the same individual may have different motivations for leaving his or her country, that these motives may change over time and often blur the distinction between economic migrants and refugees. Contrary to popular perceptions, it is not the poorest and the destitute that depart their home places to try and reach more advanced nations, since some basic financial resources and skills are necessary to afford long-distance mobility. Most migrants typically remain within the world region they were born in. For the same reason, climate and environmental changes per se are likely not enough to ignite very large extra-continental migration flows, as feared by some.

Global inequalities may be less relevant than migration networks and a “culture of migration” in shaping patterns of international migration and making them self-perpetuating processes. The very notion that promoting aid, investment, trade and other forms of exchange between countries of destination and countries of origin can help contain people’s movements may be misplaced, as closer links may turn out to actually foster the volume of migration. Finally, in spite of mounting anti-immigration fears across a number of Western countries, there is increasing evidence of a positive economic impact of migration in receiving economies. Therefore, coupled with the framing media theory, migration in Africa may not be all bad as certain media headlines make it sound.

Methodology

This paper adopted the descriptive research method. This method offers description of how and why African migrants in European, American and even African countries face negative representation in the global media organisations. This design is also suitable for this paper because it allows for explanation of the meeting point and divergence between culture, human rights, migration, causes for migration and media prejudice.

Discussion

Some media organisations are attempting to reshape the discussion, as different media sources try to break the stereotypical demonisation of migrants and capture the contribution they make to the vibrancy of host societies. A report from the Africa Independent Television (AIT) captioned ‘Post ECOWAS Seeks Ways to Curb Illegal Migration’ has it that the Economic Community of West African States, ECOWAS, wants countries in the sub-region to mainstream immigration into their national security architecture in order to effectively tackle illegal trans-border movement (AIT, 2018). According to the news station, the commission said this during the opening of a three-day workshop in Abuja on migration dialogue which brought together heads of immigration from ECOWAS member’s states and Mauritania.

According to Chouliaraki & Zaborowski (2017), European media — which African media frequently borrow from — tend to portray African migrants as helpless victims or security threats. This binary framing strips migrants of agency and complexity. African media often adopt this framing, reinforcing the same narratives. Furthermore, De Haas (2008) emphasised that while most African migration is intra-continental and economically beneficial, media outlets overwhelmingly focus on irregular migration to Europe, reinforcing stereotypes of desperation and illegality.

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Every year, millions of young African men and women risk everything, including their lives, to take on the perilous trip across dozens of borders in search of a better life. They thereby force themselves into other countries sometimes without legal documents. ECOWAS says such movements of people pose difficult questions for many governments and for the international community especially in the West African sub-region. To tackle this, the sub-regional body is formulating policies that will strengthen and build capacities for it to properly manage free movement of people. The Abuja forum comprises of various migration dialogue working groups from different West African countries and Mauritania that have come together to enhance efforts at curbing irregular migration as well as manage internal and external borders of West Africa.

From the report, it can be deduced that media stations do not pay attention to the causes of migration rather they concentrate on the effects thereby portraying the movement (migration) as illegal whether within or outside the African continent. This obviously creates stereotype in the minds of members of the public. On this note, it is important to note that there are two main aspects of migration which the media gives little or no coverage; voluntary and force migration. Just as the name implies, voluntary migration is a situation whereby people willingly, with reasons leave their places of habit to move to another place. Though, these reasons may not be justified in the area where they move in. Factors that cause voluntary migration can be described as social or economic. Some examples of social factors are:

- better living conditions.
- access to health care.
- access to good education.
- Economic factors include.
- better employment prospects.
- higher wages.

While migration can benefit countries, for example, by providing new trades, skills and a cheaper workforce, there are potential drawbacks to large scale migration; they are:

- healthcare and education services can become strained.
- a large influx of migrants can lead to housing shortages.
- cultural differences can lead to racial tensions.
- the welfare system can become strained if migrants claim benefits

According to McConville (2018), forced migration has caused millions of people around the world to be uprooted, including refugees, internally displaced persons, and migrants. People are forced to leave their home every minute and the global total of forcibly displaced people currently stands at over 65 million. 10 million of them stateless and 22 million are refugees in foreign lands (McConville, 2018. In collaboration, the Channels Television on May 7, 2018 in a headline, ‘Canada Looks to Stem Illegal Migration from Nigeria’, reported that about 2,500 migrants, mostly Nigerian nationals, entered Canada illegally in April, bringing the total so far that year to more than 7,300.

The Minister for Immigration, Ahmed Hussen was quoted by the station saying “they crossed on foot along a forest trail from New York State to Quebec province.”

According to Channels TV, the United States authorities also recently tightened their visa rules for Nigerians to try to prevent tourists from flying to the US and then hopping across the border to file Canadian refugee claims. An average of 70-80 migrants per day have been making the trip of late, said Public Safety Minister Ralph Goodale. Nearly 21,000 border jumpers were intercepted by federal police in 2017 and allowed to file a refugee claim. “Just over 90 percent of irregular migrants do not meet our criteria (for asylum) and they will have to leave Canada,” Garneau said, adding that 200 currently face imminent deportation after their refugee claims were rejected.

The first arrivals in 2016 were mostly Haitians who faced repatriation at the end of US temporary special protections granted after storms battered their desperately poor island nation. But the wave expanded in 2017 to also include Djiboutian, Eritrean, Nigerian, Pakistani, Sudanese, Syrian, Turkish and Yemeni nationals, among others. The border jumping started with the election of US President Donald Trump, who promised to expel more than 11 million undocumented migrants (Channels TV, 2018). According to Danilova (2014), the free United Kingdom newspaper *Migrant Voice* is led by migrants and is, therefore, actively bringing their opinions to the public while introducing readers to the life stories of newcomers, their aspirations and plans for the future. It draws attention to migration policies and the effects they produce, including those on the British economy. The main aims are building a more inclusive public debate and shifting the narrative to help to change the public attitude. An independent website *Migrant Solidarity in Calais* is run by a group of people in France and documents the daily abuses of refugees by the French police, while also providing them with legal advice and information on their rights. Through online media, they attempt to share accurate information with the public on the poor conditions that refugees face. This goes to show that the media is only interested in reporting the negative sides of migration; painting the migrants as less humans, who do not know their worth. No country is happy receiving migrants. The media seems to be siding nations.

Victoria Danilova of the United Nations University in 2014 opines that, all that is needed is to raise awareness about the daily experiences of migrants and photography turns out to be the perfect tool for that. The 2014 World Press Photo Award went to a moonlit image showing migrants trying to get mobile phone signals and call home, as they make their way to Europe for better life. Photo projects across Europe serve as a lens through which the local population can get to know the diversity of migration experiences and confront the stereotypes about migrants. The Migrant Photography exhibition, “Belonging,” in Belfast gives a glimpse into the lives of migrants, combining art with workshop activities, engaging the local population into a much-needed dialogue. Each portrait of a migrant is accompanied by an audio-recording of their personal story and individual experience. Another example is a global photo-project, the “Moving Walls” that showcases images of migrants and refugees depicting a wide range of often under-reported social issues (Kariithi, 2017).

Returning to the topic of the European elections, why did the far-right parties manage to gain popular support playing the anti-immigrant card? In essence, it is because there exists a widespread sense that it is impossible to change the existing social orders blaming ‘the other’ seems the only option. The answer to this problem requires creating an inclusive public sphere as an encompassing forum where opinions are shared and

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shaped and where migrants too could have a say. In fact, the internet and social media can perform this function as, despite the recent rise of cyber-racism, they have the potential to serve as a platform for public engagement and constructive dialogue at all levels.

The international community has been taking steps to acknowledge and address the link between public opinion about migrants and media. During the Second UN High-level Dialogue on International Migration and Development in October 2013, migration was recognized as the core of the international development discourse and Making Migration Work: An Eight Point Action Agenda was announced. One of its points highlights the importance of media as the means to combat xenophobia and intolerance against migrants, especially through raising public awareness about the lives of migrants, the challenges they face and the contributions they make both to host societies and countries of origin. Civil society, on its part, proposed a follow-up Five-year Action Plan that includes migration in the post-2015 development agenda and sees it as a tool to reduce poverty and promote development (Kariithi, 2017).

Meanwhile, there are initiatives to foster greater dialogue between academic and policy circles through, for example, the United Nations University Migration Network. Such explicit attention to migration as a core feature of the global development discourse certainly has the potential to turn the spotlight on the human face of migration and to change public perceptions of migrants for the better, portraying them as individuals looking for ways to contribute. Moreover, international reflections on media and migration boost efforts to protect the human rights of migrants and to highlight the responsibility media has in shaping public perceptions while ensuring that myths and rumors do not negatively affect the lives of migrants.

Conclusion

In attempting to answer the question of whether media portrayals of immigrants are reflective of actual group differences, or prejudicial in nature, the simple answer is that, in all likelihood, there are examples of both in the media. Certainly, historically, the African media has, at times, presented blatantly prejudicial and inflammatory presentations of migrants although these portrayals were themselves reflective of a less ethnically sensitive cultural past. In Portrayals of Immigrants response to changes in African and European cultures over the past forty years and criticisms from academia, the mass media have made strides to present a more diversified view of African culture. Undoubtedly, however, more progress is desirable. This is likely particularly true for the issue of immigration, which remains ambiguous in the public opinion. As such stereotypical depictions of immigrant populations in the media represent a risk fraught area in which prejudices may inadvertently be furthered.

Even if the mass media have not necessarily responsible for the development of prejudice in African culture (although prejudice is by no means a uniquely American or Western phenomenon) it can be argued that the media could be used as a force for positive change. At very least, by avoiding unfair prejudicial depictions, and presenting immigrant populations as well rounded cultural groups, the media may be capable of providing a positive arena for diversity, cultural exchange and acculturation. As is typical, the media will likely respond with such programming when the vast majority of viewers insist upon it

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